

Community Needs and Priorities for the Future of Open Data Publishing

Dryad & California Digital Library

Many institutions provide Institutional Repositories (IRs) for local management of article PDFs and, increasingly, research data. There is also a growing trend toward offering data consulting and curation services, usually based in the library. Unfortunately, the low rates of adoption/use of IRs¹ and lack of awareness among researchers about local RDM services suggest that institutional investment in RDM needs a strategic overhaul. Disciplinary and non-institutional, general data repositories such as Dryad have much higher rates of adoption than IRs because they are directly integrated with researcher workflows at key points, particularly article publishing.

Meanwhile, there has been a rapid influx of commercial solutions that look to address data requirements associated with funding and publishing. As more researchers become aware of these tools that meet their immediate needs, the research community risks losing control of and access to research data (in the same manner as published articles). The risk of rising commercialization in the data ecosystem beyond these closed access structures is the associated inaccessible costs at the institutional level.

In light of these needs and changes in the current research data landscape, Dryad and California Digital Library (CDL) are formally partnering to address researcher needs and lead an open, community-supported initiative in research data curation and publishing. This partnership is focused on combining CDL's institutional relationships, expertise, and nimble technology with Dryad's position in the researcher community, curation workflows, and publisher relationships. By working together, we will create global efficiencies and minimize needless duplication of effort across institutions, freeing up time and funds, and, in particular, allowing institutions with fewer resources to support research data publishing and ensure data remain open.

The open data space requires innovation and as such we will be integrating into researcher workflows and building a viable product to address commercial threats. This will help bring value by building broad, sustainable, and productive approaches to data curation. With both CDL and Dryad's expertise, the partnership aims to address and offer:

¹ Multiple Sources: <http://cameronneylon.net/blog/the-trouble-with-institutional-repositories/>, <http://www.dlib.org/dlib/march07/davis/03davis.html>, and https://oda.hioa.no/en/researchers-attitude-to-using-institutional-repositories-a-case-study-of-the-oslo-university-institutional-repository-duo/asset/dspace:1228/Alemayehu_MulukenWubayehu.pdf

- 1) Researchers- a higher level of curation service and integration into their normal workflows
- 2) Publishers- enhanced technical integrations and more comprehensive curation services
- 3) Institutions- a globally-accessible, community-led, low-cost alternative to commercial products that focuses on breaking down silos between publishing, libraries, and research

Our goal for this session is to gather a community of like-minded research stakeholders to help us define the features, curation approaches, etc. of a new community-led Dryad offering. Members from the Dryad and CDL team will present on the work already underway to move Dryad onto the CDL-hosted technology platform. The session will also be a source of requirements gathering and community input into our longer-term partnership roadmap and business models. The discussions that come out of the session will act as guidance for the continued development of our services that are focused on being a collaborative data publishing platform that integrates data curation/stewardship more closely into researcher workflows.